

Enhancement of Flame Resistance in Polyester Blended Furnishing Fabrics Using Dip–Nip Processing Methods

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Abstract:

Flame retardancy is essential for ensuring fire safety compliance in home-furnishing textiles such as curtains and upholstery. Polyester and polyester–cotton (PC) blended fabrics are widely used for these applications; however, their inherent flammability necessitates effective flame-retardant (FR) treatments. In this study, 100% polyester, 80:20 PC, and 67:33 PC fabrics were treated with a halogen-free flame-retardant formulation using a pad–dry–cure process with controlled dip–nip sequences (1D–1N, 2D–2N, and 4D–4N), both with and without sodium hydroxide pre-treatment. The effect of dip–nip repetition on FR uptake, vertical flammability behaviour, and washing durability was evaluated using ASTM D6413 and ISO 6330 standard test methods. The results showed a significant reduction in char length from approximately 15 cm (untreated samples) to 4.5–5.5 cm (post FR treatment). Although FR uptake increased with the number of dip–nip cycles, no substantial improvement was observed beyond the 2D–2N sequence. The treated samples retained palpable flame-retardant performance of up to four laundering cycles, indicating moderate durability of the applied finish. Among the investigated samples, the 80:20 Polyester–Cotton blend exhibited the best flame-retardant performance, attributed to enhanced interaction between the flame-retardant formulation and the hydroxyl groups present in the cellulosic component. The study demonstrates that an optimized 2D–2N sequence provides an effective balance between chemical uptake, flame-retardant performance, and durability for polyester-based home-furnishing textiles.

Keywords: Flame retardancy, Home furnishings, Laundry cycle, Nip–Dip, Polyester–cotton blends

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1. Introduction

Home-furnishing textiles such as curtains, upholstery, and decorative fabrics are widely used in interior environments but pose significant fire hazards due to their large exposed surface area and combustible nature. During ignition, these materials can accelerate flame spread and release toxic fumes, endangering occupants and property. Such fire incidents accelerate due to rapid heat release and flame propagation, highlighting the need for effective flame-retardant treatments for indoor applications. [1]

Polyester is widely used in home furnishings for its high strength, dimensional stability, and aesthetic properties; however, it exhibits thermoplastic behaviour and tends to melt and drip when heated, which can intensify fire hazards. Unlike cellulosic fibres, polyester does not readily form a protective char layer, further contributing to its higher flammability. Flame-retardant finishes applied through pad–dry cure processes improve resistance to ignition and flame propagation while maintaining acceptable fabric properties. [2]

Polyester–cotton blends are also widely used, combining the durability of polyester with the comfort of cotton. The presence of cellulosic hydroxyl groups enhances the interaction and retention of flame-retardant agents, promoting char formation and reducing flammability. This synergistic effect makes blended fabrics suitable for improved flame-retardant performance.

Although several flame-retardant finishing techniques exist, many involve complex processing or higher chemical consumption. The dip–nip (padding) method offers a simple and scalable approach, enabling controlled FR chemical pickup and uniform distribution of flame-retardant agents across the fabric surface. However, limited studies have systematically evaluated the effect of repeated dip–nip cycles on flame-retardant uptake and performance, particularly in blended fabrics. In addition, the durability of the applied finish under laundering conditions is a critical requirement for practical applications.

This study investigates the effect of controlled dip–nip sequences on flame-retardant uptake, performance, and washing durability of a halogen-free finish applied to polyester and polyester–cotton fabrics.

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2. Material and Methods

2.1 Materials

Three woven fabrics 100% polyester (S1), 80:20 Polyester–Cotton (S2), and 67:33 Polyester–Cotton (S3); sample code mentioned within brackets, were procured from the local market. The fabrics were of plain-weave structure and commonly used for home-furnishing applications. Fibre composition and blend ratios were confirmed using standard chemical solubility methods (ISO 1833) and burn tests. A halogen-free phosphorus-based flame-retardant formulation (Flame Guard–DPS, supplied by Sarex, India) was used for finishing. The fabric specifications are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 - Physical and Structural Properties of Fabrics

Fabric Property	S1 (100% PES)	S2 (80:20 PC)	S3 (67:33 PC)
EPI	132	98	92
PPI	64	78	56
Warp Count	40	40	30
West Count	40	40	30
Warp Crimp (%)	4.24	4.27	4.35
West Crimp (%)	6.28	4.50	5.70
GSM (g/m ²)	90	112	109
Thickness (mm)	0.20	0.22	0.23

2.2 Pre-treatment

All fabric samples were initially washed in accordance with ISO 6330:2012 to remove impurities and residual finishes. Alkali pre-treatment was performed using aqueous NaOH under controlled conditions to enhance surface wettability while limiting fibre damage (weight loss < 5%). Different NaOH concentrations (5, 10, and 15 g/L) were evaluated along with varying treatment temperatures (70 °C, 90 °C & 110 °C) and durations of (30 minutes, 45 minutes & 60 minutes), keeping a material-to-liquor ratio of 1:100, to optimise the process; optimised values shown in Table 2. The required NaOH concentration was calculated using Equation (1).

$$C=(S \times P)/100 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (1)}$$

where C is the concentration (g/L), S is the stock solution strength, and P is the percentage dilution. Based on experimental trials, an optimum condition of 10 g/L NaOH at 90 °C for 45 min was selected for further trials. The weight loss of the fabric samples due to pre-treatment was calculated using Equation (2).

$$\text{“Weight Loss(%)”} = (W1 - W2)/W1 \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation (2)}$$

where W1 and W2 are the fabric weights before and after treatment, the observed weight loss (1.87–4.17%) indicates controlled surface modification without significant fibre degradation. Pre-treatment, however, showed no significant influence on flame-retardant performance and was therefore excluded from further optimization [3].

Table 2 - Optimized test-bath variables

Parameter	Concentration (10 gpl)	Temp. (90°C)	Time (45 min)
Weight Loss (%)	1.87	3.21	4.17

2.3. Flame-Retardant Application

Flame-retardant (FR) finishing was carried out using a laboratory padding mangle with an aqueous halogen-free FR formulation (160 g/L, as received, without additional additives). The fabrics were subjected to controlled dip–nip sequences, namely 1 dip–1 nip (1D–1N), 2 dip–2 nip (2D–2N), and 4 dip–4 nip (4D–4N), as illustrated in Figures 1–3.

In each cycle on the padding mangle, the fabric was immersed (dip) in the FR solution for 20 minutes, and squeezed (nip), completing one cycle. The padding operation was carried out under controlled conditions with a nip pressure of 1.75 kg/cm² and roller speed of 150 RPM, maintaining a uniform wet pick-up of approximately 70 ± 2% (70% expression). After completion of the respective dip–nip sequences, the treated samples were cured in an oven at 125°C for 5 minutes. The flame-retardant add-on (%) was calculated based on percentage weight increase using Equation (3).

Figure 1 - One dip, one nip

Figure 2 - Two dip, two nip

Figure 3 - Four dip four nip

“Add-on(%)” = $(W2 - W1) / W1 \times 100$ Equation (3)

where W1 and W2 represent the fabric weight before and after treatment, respectively.

2.4. Evaluation of Fabric Properties

The structural and mechanical properties of untreated and flame-retardant-treated fabrics were evaluated using standard test methods. Fabric thickness was measured according to ASTM D1777, areal density (GSM) as per ASTM D3776, crimp (%) according to ASTM D3883, and tensile strength using ASTM D5035 (strip method). All samples were conditioned at $65 \pm 2\%$ relative humidity and $27 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ before testing. Flame-retardant performance was assessed using the vertical flammability test (ASTM D6413), where char length was measured after flame exposure. All tests were conducted in triplicate, and average values are reported. The same testing procedures were applied to S1, S2, and S3 fabrics to ensure consistent and comparative evaluation. [5]

2.5 Washing fastness

ISO 105-C06 is the standard test method for assessing the resistance of textile colors to domestic and commercial laundering. Since the fabrics were not given the dyeing treatment, this method was used to assess the fabrics' resistance to the removal of FR applied to them.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Effect of Nipping–Dipping Cycles on Add-On

Table 3 shows that the addition of flame-retardant increased with dip–nip cycles, from 0.50–0.60% at 1D–1N to ~0.89–1.11% at 2D–2N, indicating improved chemical uptake. However, a further increase to 4D–4N cycle showed a negligible change (0.92–1.11%), suggesting saturation of the fabric structure. Polyester–cotton blends (S2 and S3) exhibited slightly better add-on due to enhanced interaction of the flame-retardant with the hydroxyl groups present in the cellulosic component compared to S1.

Table 3 - %Add-on of the FR solution on the fabric sample

Sample code	1D–1N (%)	2D–2N (%)	4D–4N (%)
S1	0.50	1.11	1.11
S2	0.50	0.89	1.07
S3	0.60	0.92	0.92

Thus, increasing the dip–nip cycles beyond 2D–2N did not significantly increase the add-on percentage, indicating saturation of flame-retardant uptake, while increasing chemical consumption without corresponding improvement in flame-retardant performance. Therefore, 1D–1N and 2D–2N sequences were identified as optimal processing conditions and selected for further experimental evaluation. [4]

3.2 Effect of Nipping–Dipping Cycles on Fabric Structure and Strength

3.2.1 Effect of Nipping–Dipping Cycles on Fabric Structural Parameters

Table 1 shows the fabric properties of the reference (untreated) samples. The structural properties of FR-treated fabrics (without pre-treatment) are presented in Table 4. Besides the usual coding of S1, S2, S3, N & D, the numbers 1, 2, & 4 indicate the nip-dip cycles.

Table 4 - Fabric properties of samples with FR treatment and without pre-treatment

Sample code	Thickness (mm)	GSM	Count (Nc)		Threads/inch		Crimp %	
			Warp	Weft	EPI	PPI	Warp	Weft
S1D1N1	0.22	90.05	40	40	131	62	4.24	6.28
S1D2N2	0.22	91	40	40	130	59	4.24	6.28
S1D4N4	0.22	91	40	40	130	59	4.24	6.28
S2D1N1	0.22	112.06	40	40	95	74	4.27	4.48
S2D2N2	0.22	113	40	40	95	73	4.27	4.5
S2D4N4	0.22	113.2	40	40	93	72	4.27	4.5
S3D1N1	0.23	109.06	30	30	90	56	4.35	5.7
S3D2N2	0.23	110	30	30	89	55	4.35	5.7

No significant variation was observed in thickness, GSM, yarn count, thread density (EPI/PPI), or crimp percentage across different dip–nip cycles, with all values remaining consistent within experimental limits. The results in Table 4 further confirm that FR treatment has a negligible influence on fabric structural characteristics, which can be attributed to the relatively low FR add-on levels (0.5% – 1.11%), as discussed in Section 3.1, combined with controlled padding conditions that enable uniform chemical deposition without inducing fibre swelling, compaction, or yarn displacement. Thus, the absence of measurable structural changes suggests that repeated dip–nip processing does not alter fabric construction or geometry, thus preserving the dimensional stability and structural integrity of both polyester and polyester–cotton blended fabrics, irrespective of pre-treatment and the number of dip–nip cycles.

The one-way ANOVA for GSM is presented in Table 5.

Null hypothesis (H0): The FR treatment does not significantly affect the GSM of S1 (1D-1N).

Alternate hypothesis (H1): The FR treatment has a significant influence on the GSM of S1 (1D-1N).

Table 5 - ANOVA for the selected model GSM

Anova: Single Factor				
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
UT	3	311	103.6667	142.3333
FRT	3	311.17	103.7233	142.47

Sour. Of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Between Groups	0.0048	1	0.0048	3.38E-05	0.9956
Within Groups	569.6067	4	142.4017		

The p-value of 0.996 indicates that the null hypothesis holds. Thus, statistically, the applied FR treatment does not significantly influence the GSM of the fabrics. The same can be done for the other samples and other nip-dip cycles.

3.2.2 Effect of Dip–Nip Cycles on Tensile Strength (Warp Direction)

The warp-way tensile test results (Table 6) show that the FR treatment reduced the maximum load of 100% polyester (S1) from 45.48 to 39.31 Kgf (~13.6%) and decreased strain, indicating increased stiffness.

Table 6 - Effect of Nipping–Dipping Cycles on Tensile Strength in Warp Direction

Sample Code	Treatment	Avg. Maximum Load (kgf)	Avg. Deflection at Max Load (mm)	Avg. % Strain at Max Load
S1	Untreated	45.48	54.17	27.09
S2	Untreated	52.13	40.92	20.46
S3	Untreated	46.11	35.40	17.70
S1	FR Treated	39.31	39.56	19.78
S2	FR Treated	51.07	36.66	18.33
S3	FR Treated	47.65	36.26	18.13

In contrast, the 80:20 Polyester–Cotton blend (S2) exhibited only a minor strength loss (~2%), while the 67:33 blend (S3) showed slight improvement (46.11 to 47.65 Kgf) with comparable strain. Overall, FR treatment adversely affects pure polyester, whereas polyester–cotton blends retain or show slight improvement, likely due to better fibre–matrix interaction.

3.2.3 Effect of Dip–Nip Cycles in Tensile Strength (Weft Direction)

The weft-way tensile test results (Table 7) indicate that FR treatment increased the maximum load of 100% polyester

(S1) from 33.76 to 42.23 Kgf (~25%) with negligible change in strain, suggesting structural stiffening due to enhanced inter-yarn friction rather than intrinsic fibre strengthening.

The 80:20 Polyester–Cotton blend (S2) showed a moderate load increase (~7%) with a slight reduction in strain, while the 67:33 blend (S3) exhibited a smaller improvement (~5%) accompanied by reduced extensibility. Overall, FR treatment in the weft direction promotes fabric consolidation and inter-yarn cohesion, maintaining or improving load-bearing capacity, particularly in blended fabrics, with minimal compromise to structural integrity.

Table 7 - Effect of Nipping–Dipping Cycles on Tensile Strength in Weft Direction

Sample Code	Treatment	Avg. Maximum Load (kgf)	Avg. Deflection at Max Load (mm)	Avg. % Strain at Max Load
S1	Untreated	33.76	27.67	13.83
S2	Untreated	46.15	51.45	25.73
S3	Untreated	57.51	46.70	23.35
S1	FR Treated	42.23	27.90	13.95
S2	FR Treated	49.33	47.94	23.97
S3	FR Treated	60.29	44.21	22.10

3.3 Vertical Flammability Performance

Vertical flammability results (ASTM D6413) in Table 8 show that untreated fabrics exhibited higher char lengths of 9.5 cm (S1), 15.0 cm (S2), and 15.0 cm (S3), indicating rapid flame propagation.

After FR treatment, char length was reduced to 5.5 cm (S1), 4.5 cm (S2), and 5.0 cm (S3). All treated samples showed negligible after-flame and after-glow times (~0–1 s), confirming self-extinguishing behaviour. Polyester–cotton blends (S2 and S3) exhibit better flame retardancy than 100% polyester, mainly due to the better attachment of the FR chemical with the cellulosic component of the fabric substrate. No significant difference was observed between

Table 8 - Vertical flammability test results (ASTM D6413)

Sample code	State	Dip–Nip	After-flame Time (s)	After-glow Time (s)	Char length (cm)	Sample code
S1	UT	–	3	2	9.5	S1
S1	FRT	2D-2N 4D-4N	Negligible	Negligible	5.5	S1
S2	UT	–	7	10	15.0	S2
S2	FRT	2D-2N 4D-4N	Negligible	Negligible	4.5	S2
S3	UT	–	7	10	15.0	S3

Note: UT = Untreated (without FR), FRT = FR Treated

** Untreated fabrics exhibited char lengths of approximately 15 cm, which decreased to 4.5–5.5 cm after flame-retardant application.*

2D–2N and 4D–4N treatments, indicating saturation beyond 2D–2N, with the 80:20 blend (S2) showing the best performance with the lowest char length.

3.4 Washing Durability of Flame-Retardant Finish

The washing durability results of the FR finish (ISO 6330) shown in Table 9 show a gradual increase in char length with successive laundering, indicating partial loss of the finish. For S1, char length increased from 5.5 to 7.0 cm after 4 washes, while blends showed better retention, with S2 increasing from 4.5 to 5.6 cm and S3 from 5.0 to 6.2 cm. Despite this, all FR treated samples maintained lower char lengths than untreated fabrics up to 4 washes, confirming retained flame retardancy. However, after the 5th wash, char

Table 9 - Effect of Washing on Flame-Retardant Performance (Char Length)

Sample code	Wash Cycle	Char Length (cm)
S1*	0	5.5
S1	1	5.8
S1	2	6.2
S1	3	6.5
S1	4	7.0
S2 *	0	4.5
S2	1	4.8
S2	2	5.0
S2	3	5.3
S2	4	5.6
S3*	0	5.0
S3	1	5.3
S3	2	5.6
S3	3	5.9
S3	4	6.2

Note: * stands for unwashed

lengths of all samples approached those of the untreated fabrics, indicating near-complete loss of FR effectiveness. The improved durability in blends is attributed to stronger FR–cellulose interaction. Overall, the FR system exhibits moderate durability, remaining effective up to 4 laundering cycles.

4. Conclusion

This study evaluated the effect of dip–nip processing on the flame-retardant performance, structural stability, mechanical behaviour, and washing durability of polyester and polyester–cotton fabrics. The application of a halogen-free FR finish significantly reduced char length from 9.5–15.0 cm to 4.5–5.5 cm, with negligible after-flame and after-glow, confirming effective flame retardancy.

FR add-on increased slightly (~0.5–1.1%) with dip–nip cycles, with no significant improvement beyond 2D–2N, indicating saturation and establishing it as the optimal condition. Polyester–cotton blends showed better performance than 100% polyester due to enhanced interaction with cellulosic components.

Structural properties remained unchanged, confirming that the process preserves fabric integrity, while blended fabrics exhibited better mechanical stability than 100% polyester fabrics. The FR finish showed moderate durability, retaining up to four wash cycles.

Overall, the 2D–2N dip–nip process provides an effective balance between flame-retardant performance, durability, and process efficiency, with the 80:20 Polyester–Cotton blend showing the best performance for home-furnishing applications due to lower char length.

References :

- [1] Horrocks, A. R., & Price, D. (2008). *Advances in flame retardant materials*. Woodhead Publishing
- [2] Dong, S., Y.-T. Huang, X. Zhang, S.-S. Cheng, X.-W. Cheng, and J.-P. Guan. 2024. “Enhancing the Flame Retardancy of Polyester/Cotton Blend Fabrics Using Biobased Urea–Phytate Salt.” *Materials* 17 (6):1346. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17061346>
- [3] Kassie, B. B., Fentahun, H., & Daget, T. M. (2024). Optimization of combined pre-treatment process for bleaching of cotton woven fabric using Box–Behnken design. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2024.2396904>
- [4] Hebeish, A., El-Naggar, M. E., Fouda, M. M. G., Ramadan, M. A., Al-Deyab, S. S., & El-Rafie, M. H. (2011). Highly effective antibacterial textiles containing green synthesized silver nanoparticles. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 86(2), 936–940. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2011.05.048>
- [5] Ghosh, A., & Mal, P. (2019). Testing of fibres, yarns and fabrics and their recent developments. In *Fibres to smart textiles* (pp. 221–256). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9780429446511-12>

